

COPING MECHANISMS OF GENDER QUEER INSTRUCTORS ON THEIR PROFESSIONAL AND PERSONAL LIFE

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ABSTRACT

The issue about gender queer instructors in the field of education is a phenomenon that is present nowadays. Due to this belief of heteronormativity, prejudices and discrimination emanates which implicate the psychological being of gender queer particularly those belong in the educational institution. This study sought to discover and understand the difficulties being faced by gender queer instructors and how they cope with it. This would direct to a better coping mechanism which will enhance their present situation as to be belong in the heterosexual group. Through this study, their challenges and coping mechanism were further defined which provide a better working condition in their profession and buoyant personal life which will further signify their enormous contribution on the field of Education. The Researcher employed the qualitative descriptive method of research with the unstructured questionnaire as the primary data gathering instrument. According to the study, gender queers are experiencing enormous different challenges such as stigmatization, prejudices and discrimination, leeriness and disdain on their both professional and personal life. In connection, gender queers should be geared themselves with highest educational background and skills that they could in order for them to cope with the majority of the challenges brought by stressful social environment both on their professional and personal life. The following conclusions were generated from this study: First, gender queers are experiencing challenges relevant to their professional and personal life that creates a stressful social environment. Second, gender queers are experiencing psychological distress due to professional and personal challenges. Third, most of the gender queer instructors geared themselves with high educational attainment to cope on the challenges that they are encountering both on professional and personal life. Fourth, field of education should provide standard professional ethics applicable for all gender queer instructors to eliminate stereotyping which is the source of professional and personal challenges of gender queers' life.

Keywords: Discipline of the Study: Psychology, Sociology, Behavioral Science, Concept Investigated: Queer Theory, Social constructionism, Theory of positivism, Methods and Process: Qualitative Research, Unstructured questionnaire, Country: Philippines